

ENHANCING SPEAKING COMPREHENSION ABILITIES OF STUDENTS OF ACADEMIC LYCEUM

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Abstract. *Strengthening speaking comprehension is vital for learners of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), as it equips them to engage effectively with specialized texts relevant to their academic or professional domains. To achieve this, it is important to implement strategies that align with their specific needs and goals.*

By focusing on the unique linguistic demands of their field and providing purposeful speaking practice, ESP learners can develop the skills necessary to interpret and apply information from various discipline-specific texts, such as technical manuals, research articles, or business reports. Tailored instruction and thoughtfully chosen materials are key to fostering their success.

Keywords: *speaking skill, comprehension, ESP class, ESP learner, speaking strategies, pre-while-post activities.*

In today's globalized world, the ability to speak and comprehend specialized situations is an essential skill for learners of English language. Whether in academic, technical, or professional fields, effective reading comprehension enables learners to access, analyze, and apply knowledge pertinent to their areas of expertise. The increasing demand for specialists who can engage with discipline-specific materials in English underscores the importance of developing tailored strategies to enhance this skill.

This article explores the challenges of students of academic lyceum face in speaking comprehension and offers practical methods to address these challenges. By focusing on authentic materials, learner-centered approaches, and targeted strategies, educators can support students in building the necessary competencies to thrive in their respective domains. Through a combination of theoretical insights and practical applications, this discussion aims to provide a comprehensive framework for improving speaking comprehension skills among ESP learners. In addition, the “internationalization” of education and increasing academic mobility requires the skills to continue learning after graduation in accordance with «Life Long Learning» concept, as well as skills to carry out professional activities in a foreign language environment. The transition to a knowledge society, as highlighted by Maximova (2016, pp. 1003–1010), presents new opportunities for the academic and educational communities while setting higher expectations for the linguistic competence of modern professionals. Furthermore, the rapid pace of cultural globalization underscores the growing importance of preparing high school graduates with strong intercultural communication skills and the capacity to navigate international interactions effectively. Another category of learners in a classroom is the visual learners who best respond to visual learning stimuli. Besides learning from these visual stimuli, visual learners also learn by observing what others do in a learning session. This category of learners studies best when they are given visual learning stimuli like charts, diagrams, pictures, or formulae written on the blackboard. This category of learners is usually creative in applying their learning outcomes, observant in nature and not easily distracted (Arthurs, 2007; Gilakjani, 2012).

In today's interconnected world, the ability to engage across cultural boundaries is no longer optional but essential for personal and professional success. Advanced proficiency in foreign languages has become a critical factor in enhancing one's competitiveness in the global labor market, offering a distinct advantage in virtually every profession. By fostering these skills, individuals are better equipped to adapt to diverse environments, build meaningful connections, and excel in an increasingly interconnected and multicultural workforce.

Speaking comprehension is a fundamental skill that lies at the heart of the reading process and plays a crucial role in achieving its primary objectives. It is a defining feature of proficient readers, who can significantly contribute to societal development through their ability to process and apply information effectively. This skill involves more than simply understanding text; it demands precision, independence in speaking, a deep grasp of content, and an efficient pace. Additionally, it encompasses a genuine enjoyment of reading, the ability to adapt to diverse reading purposes, and active engagement with various events and ideas presented in the text. A strong reader also demonstrates the capacity to form and articulate opinions, think critically, and approach content with creativity, making reading comprehension an invaluable tool for personal and collective growth.

The development of speaking comprehension skills of professionally-oriented texts is one of the most important educational tasks in teaching English to lyceum students. First of all, speaking comprehension is a must in contemporary post-industrial societies. In the era of digitalization students need to upgrade their skills and strategies (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010, pp. 179-225). Secondly, the variety of texts students encounter has significantly expanded, with "electronic" texts now complementing traditional "paper" formats. Since speaking strategies differ based on the type of text, teaching methods for developing speaking comprehension must be adapted accordingly. This is particularly evident in the context of academic reading in the Social Sciences and Humanities, where learners and educators face the added complexity of navigating diverse styles, formats, and genres, making the teaching process more challenging.

Classroom activities can maximize learners' speaking speed and efforts. They do not tell anything about how language is used to communicate ideas (Kurland, 2013)

The significance of the study stems from the special attention educational systems pay for developing students' reading skills to improve their reading comprehension. The current study can be described as one of the new studies examining the effect of visual word formulation on reading comprehension (Khasawneh, M. 2020)

Speaking comprehension is a vital skill for English learners, serving as a cornerstone for their overall success in language acquisition. For many, mastering this skill is essential to unlocking progress in other areas of language learning, such as writing, listening, and speaking. When learners develop strong speaking skills, they often experience accelerated growth in their linguistic abilities, as reading serves as a foundation for expanding vocabulary, improving grammar, and fostering critical thinking.

Effective speaking is best understood as an interactive and dynamic process, requiring the learner to actively engage with the text to construct and uncover meaning. This process transcends basic decoding of words, encompassing higher-order skills such as interpretation, critical analysis, and the ability to connect ideas within and beyond the text. Such an approach fosters deeper understanding and encourages readers to think critically about the material, enriching their learning experience.

By adopting this active speaking strategy, learners can significantly enhance their comprehension abilities. Moreover, this method promotes the development of fluency and builds confidence in using English, as it empowers learners to independently explore and interact with diverse content. Over time, this engagement strengthens not only linguistic proficiency but also cognitive skills essential for effective communication and lifelong learning.

Considering the challenges mentioned, the author examines the impact of lyceum students speaking in teaching English for mechanical design and manufacturing. The exploration focuses on three key aspects: pre-class reading task detection, where students' preparation and comprehension are assessed; while-reading teaching, which involves guiding students through the material to enhance understanding and engagement; and teaching of speaking, which emphasizes consolidating knowledge, applying concepts, and encouraging critical reflection. This structured approach aims to improve students' technical language proficiency and their ability to engage with specialized content effectively.

Although English speaking for mechanical design and manufacturing is a branch of traditional English reading, the obvious difference from traditional speaking lies in the concentrated presentation of professional knowledge of mechanical design and manufacturing. It is important for teachers to explain English vocabulary, grammar and text interpretation in class, but the study of mechanical design and manufacturing expertise should be the top priority of English reading course.

Teachers assign learning tasks at the beginning of the semester, group students, and let students find information, discuss in groups and cooperate to complete topic presentation reports. After each group completes the report, the teacher gives some evaluation on their performance, which make the students have a better understanding of the material they report and also bring some confidence and interests in special English learning.

Through pre-class preparation, students have a deeper understanding of the topics discussed, which not only aroused their interest in language learning, but also deepened their learning of the professional knowledge. Pre-class task detection based on professional knowledge makes students no longer think that teaching of reading is just listening to teachers who explain vocabulary and articles as usual, but really integrated into specific professional knowledge learning, which embodies the principle that teaching of speaking content meets learners' specific needs.

Speaking materials provide substantial linguistic input (Bell, 1998), which is required for language learning. So, speaking provides a rich source for developing learners' linguistic competencies for reading as well writing which can only be improved by applying careful reading strategies. Researchers point out the importance of extensive reading skills, but what does extensive reading entail? Successful extensive reading requires the following attributes (Maley, 2009):

- Speaking often and in a large quantity
- Speaking of a wide variety of topics and genres
- Speaking content that is interesting, compelling and persuasive
- Speaking books which students should select on their own
- Speaking for pleasure and information
- Speaking is compulsory to improve all other skills namely listening, speaking and writing skills.

Teaching focuses on "articles" rather than "sentences", and on "gist" rather than "language analysis". Classroom speaking activities should start with the analysis of theme, text structure and paragraph cohesion, and teachers should guide students to pay attention to understanding the author's central idea and text structure. In the continuous reading process, they should grasp the specific structure of relevant reading models and improve their overall understanding and grasp of the article.

There are several ways to understand the central idea of discourse and long and difficult sentences and words in the following. The summary of the central idea can be carried out from the following aspects: 1) Focusing on the title of the article. 2) Focusing on the central sentence of the article or the topic sentence of the paragraphs. 3) Focusing on the cohesive sentences and paragraphs of the article. 4) Focusing on the beginning and the end of the article. 5) Focusing on lyrical and argumentative sentences.

Merrett and Wheldell (1990) mention in their book *Positive Teaching in the Primary School* four interesting points which help effective classroom behavior management. The main learning goals in the primary school are to help students read, write, and calculate. To have enough time for these subjects positive teaching gives tips to have a comfortable atmosphere. "Positive teachers concern themselves with what children actually do rather than speculating about unconscious motives or processes which may be thought to underlie their pupils' behavior" (Marrett & Wheldall, 1990, p. 11).

In conclusion, the development of reading skills is a cornerstone of educational success and personal growth. Speaking goes beyond mere word recognition; it encompasses comprehension, critical thinking, and the ability to connect ideas. By fostering a positive and engaging learning environment, educators can inspire students to actively participate in the reading process, transforming it into a dynamic and enriching experience.

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